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**Ripples in the Moves: Choreographing the group in Rukmini Devi's
Pancāpsara sarōvara- The Lake of the five Water Nymphs**

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Abstract

Group choreographies in the dance form of Bharatanatyam was unheard of till the 1940's though traditional dance-drama forms like Kuravanji nataka and Bhagavatha mela nataka existed as religious and court practises since the period of Chola and Vijayanagara empire in the 10th and 14th CE respectively. With the nationalistic vision and changing socio-cultural fabric during the pre-independence, Bharatanatyam, a solo dance form, began to be adapted to be presented on the proscenium by a few who took liberty to make innovations to its format. This paper analyses the component structures, features and style of one such choreography in Sabari Mōkṣam, a dance-drama work of Rukmini Devi. The preliminary movement analysis is based on dance texts of Abhinaya Darpana. Movement analysis undertaken here involves interpretive discussion on the technique of Pancāpsara sarōvara, a scene that depicts the dance of five water nymphs under the surface of a lake. The paper shows how the scene offers a fantastic prologue to the unfolding drama through different strategies of choreography.

Key words: Bharatanatyam, Choreography, Dance- drama, movement analysis, Rukmini Devi

Introduction

Bharatanatyam or Sadir dance, practised by the devadasi community in the temples and courts of Tamil Nadu, had begun to be taken up and performed by aficionados from different communities from the early 20th century onwards after the move to abolish dance as an offering at temples began from 1930 onwards. As the socio-cultural profile of the dance form changed during this time, its aesthetics also underwent transitions to suit the changing perceptions of a country coming to terms with its nationalistic awakenings. Bharatanatyam, a traditionally solo form of dance, began to be adapted to different formats of dance. Among the notable few who

explored the form and began presenting in different formats were Rukmini Devi with dance-drama- 'Kutrāla Kuravanji',1944; Ram Gopal in his thematic solos like 'Lord Shiva danced', 1948; Travancore sisters- Lalitha and Padmini in duet dancing for 'Dance of Shiva and Mohini' in motion picture Kannika,1947; and Mrinalini Sarabhai with her dance-drama, 'Manushya',1949. Amongst these pioneers, Rukmini Devi is one of the early choreographers who made innovations in adapting the solo form to collective dancing especially through her group compositions¹. This paper has attempted to analyse one of her group choreography works, the dance of the *Pancāpsaras* from her Ramayana production, *Sabari Mōkṣam* and shows how different choreographic strategies and components of technique are used to create meaningful expressions in a group choreography. The title of this paper 'ripples in the moves' is analogous to the typical technique and special movements Rukmini Devi used in this particular scene of the dance of water nymphs.

Music and Story line

Sabari Mōkṣam, choreographed by Rukmini Devi in 1965, is an excerpt from *Aranya Kāṇḍam*, the third book of Valmiki Rāmāyana that deals with the abduction of Sita by Ravana. *Pancāpsaras* is the first scene of *Sabari Mōkṣam* as the dance-drama unfolds. Sri Rama, Sita and Lakshmana who are in the precincts of the hermitage of sage Agastya on the banks of a beautiful lake hear sounds of music and dance coming from inside a lake called *Pancāpsara sarōvara*, a creation of the sage Mandakarni. As the story goes, five apsaras (water nymphs) were sent by the gods to entertain the sage and distract him from his powerful penance. The sounds of drums, instruments and music of the unseen dance emanate from underneath the lake where the sage witnesses the performance of the beautiful apsaras. This dance drama based on Valmiki's Ramayana slokas in Sanskrit has music composed by Mysore Vasudevacharyar, who taught vocal music at Rukmini Devi's dance school- Kalakshetra. *The Pancāpsara* scene is set to *Sriranjani rāgam and Misrachāpu tālam*. The scene opens after the usual preliminary invocatory slokas sung in five ragas. These slokas in praise of Ganeśa, Valmiki, Hanumān, Ramayana and Sri Rāma are sung in *nāttai, gaula, ārabhi, sri* and *varāli* ragas respectively. The usage of these

¹ This is the second article where I have undertaken analysis of the choreographer's dance-drama, *śabari Mōkṣam*. My other article focused on Jatāyu and śurpanakhā pātrapraveśam of the same dance-drama and attempted to contextualise her works against nationalism

ghana pancaka ragas typical of Tyagaraja's Pañcaratna kritis of carnatic music seem to emphasise the grandeur and importance of the Ramayana epic that unfolds.

Fig:1 Geography of Kalakshetra Proscenium stage

Movements and Analysis

Panĉāpsara sarōvara, the first scene in *Sabari Mōksham*, the fourth in the Ramayana series of Rukmini Devi, is performed by a group of five dancers (who will be henceforth mentioned as *a*, *b*, *c*, *d* and *e*). The first line of verse sung opens to misty environs consisting of creepers, shrubs and trees. These are hazy outlines painted against the cyclorama on which is projected a blue- green light that combines to create an ambience of a forest enveloped with mist against a watery translucence of the lake. The background and gradually the stage are enveloped by this light creating an ethereal feel. Focus then shifts to the front stage (fig-1) as diffused light starts filling in and dancers appear from the wings with the beginning of the swaras- M, D M G G R.... Five female dancers as apsaras are dressed in off-white skirts with their blouse, *pallu* and back-seat in varying hues of rose, pink, navy blue, light green and blue-green., The costumes in sea and moss green, lotus pink and a pool deep purple adds to the illusion of the lake where they dance (Ramnarayan,2003). The song is set to misra chāpu in madhyama kāla. As this is a nritta oriented scene, the use of this particular tāla and laya acquires significance as it gives a better base to shift to druta kāla whenever required.

TABLE-1

Set. no	Song	Kaṇakhu/ Rhythm	Aḍavus, important feet movements, śira, hasta, grīva, dṛiṣṭi bheda and arm movements ²	
I	M , ḍ M G G R S R G M , N D M D N G R ,	Takatakita-4	a & b: kunčita bhramari anticlockwise; teiyāteihi c: teiyāteihi; ēkapada bhramari d & e: mōḥita utplavana- sideways	
II	D N G R N D R S G R , S N D R S , N D M D M , G R S ,	Takadimi-2	a,b,c,d and e: Usi	
		a&d:	Takita taka;	Utplavana (front and back)
			Taka;	Vēgini backwards
			Takita taka;	————— Tateitām diteitām (muzhumaṇḍi, gāruḍam, bhramari)
			————— Takitatakita;	Vēgini (front)
		c,e &b	takita	Tīrmāna aḍavu ————— (kitatakatarikitatom)
			Takita takita-2	Utplavana (front); teididitei
Takadimi takita	āyata (stamp and moving back-kuttaṇa)			
III	Ḣ Ḣ Ḣ G R G N D N	Takadimi takatakita	Teiyāteihi	
	S ; N G R S N D M D N R S N	Takadimi-4	Usi aḍavu	
IV	D M M , G R S Ḣ S R G M	Takatakita;	a & d: mōḥita utplavana sideways c,e & b: kartari utplavana	
		Takadimi;	a & d : 2 nd tateitam nattaḍavu(2 nd half)- levels-sama, muzhumaṇḍi & sama	
			c, e & b: kartari utplavana	
		Takita	a,b, c, d, e: teididitei ————— (kiṭatakatarikiṭatom)	
V	Druta kala M , D M ta ka ja ṇu kit a tom	Takadimi-3	a & d: kuditu mettaḍavu; diditei-2 (preritam, ayatam)	

² All descriptions of angika abhinaya are according to Nandikeshwara's Abhinayadarpana. ed & trnsl Ghosh, Manomohan .1975.

	(M , D M G G R S R G M ,)		c, e & b: diditei-2 (prēitam-ayatam-kaṭakāmukam to alapadma; teyyateihi)
	N D M D ta ja ṇum , (N D M D N G R ,)	Takatakita takita	Moṭita utplavana; diditei
		Takadimi takadimi	Taṭhimettu (gesturing instruments)
	Ku kum tari N D R S (D N G R N D R S)	Takadimi takadimi	Alternate legs thrown front; diditei deiditei
VI	Da ṇam , ta ri ta R S , N D M (G R , S N D R S , N D M)	Takita-2	a & d tattimettu c, b & e: moṭita utplavana(sides)
		Takita takita	a & d : Moṭita utplavana (backwards) c, b & e : moṭita utplavana (front)
	Da ṇam, kit a ta (D M , G R S)	Takita-2	Muzhumaṇḍi; ayata with one leg thrown at an angle above ground (5 th ta tei tam position)
VII	, N D N G R G da ṇa ta jam;(N D N G R G N D N S ;)	Ta ; takadimi-3	Usi- vēgini
	N G R S N D	Takita takita	a & d: čhalana
	ta kun ta ri jam , da ṇa jam (M D N R S , N D M)	Takita-3	a & d: Utplavanam; theermana aḍavu-2 (kiṭatakadarikiṭatom)
	M , G R S ta din giṇa tom , (M , G R S N S R G M)	Takita takita takadimi	a & d: Taṭhimettu (with vēgini off from stage)
VIII	N G R S N D ta kun ta ri jam , da ṇa jam M , G R S ta din giṇa tom , (N G R S N D M D N R S , N D M M , G R S N S R G M)	takadimi	c, b & e: čhalana (walk back together with gestures of instruments)
IX	Ta tah kartum tapō vighnam	Takita takatakita-2	b, c & e: taṭhimettu
	Dēvei sarvairniyōjitāha	Takadimi-2; takadimi taka; dimi	Kartari utplavana (sides); vēgini (with self-round to change positions); diditei
	Pradhānāpsarasāh panća vidhyuçalita varčasaha	Takadimi-3; takatakita-2; takita-2	Taṭhimettu; kartari utplavana (front); diditei-2- entire sequence repeated twice
	(Madyama kāla)	Takita-2	c, b & e: kartari utplavana

X	D ; N ; D M G , R		<i>a & d</i> : diditei (tatti); diditei (natti) (entry from left)	
		takatakita	<i>a,b,c,d,e</i> : ekapāda bhramari	
	S , N Ḍ Ṇ S	Takita takita	<i>c,b,e</i> : taṭhimettu <i>a&d</i> : diditei (tatti; diditei (natti)	
	; R G M , D N D ,	<i>C,B,E</i> :takatakita-2		Teididitei-2
		<i>a & d</i> : (druta kala) ————— takatakಿತatakatakita;-2		Teididitei (natti)-2; kunčita bhramari
S N D M N	<i>c,b,e</i> : takatakita		Teididitei-2	
	<i>a & d</i> : drutakala ————— Takadimi takatakita (ta)		Kuṭhaṇam; tirmāna adavu (druta kala- takitatakadarikiṭatom)	
XI	D ; N , S R G M G R S , N D N R S , N D , Ḍ M , G R Ṇ S R G M	Takita takadimi takadimi-2; takita taka; takita taka	<i>a,b,c,d,e</i> together come to a circular formation- round fling of one leg, sama ćalanam ; moṭita utplavana (sides) ; tirmāna adavu	
XII	Takajanutām, tat, tat, takadimi tām,	Takadimi-4	<i>b,a,c,e</i> : come around d-one feet sama, other kunčita outstretched, bhramara hands D: moṭita maṇḍala; parshva sući- twice	
	Dhīm tām	————— Takita takita	<i>b,a,c,e</i> - ćalana <i>d</i> : moṭita maṇḍala; sama	
	Kita daṇata	takatakita	<i>b,a,c,e</i> : continue ćalana <i>d</i> : usi	
XIII	Jamtaritakatōm kukuntari kitatōm	————— Takadimi-4	<i>d,b,a,e</i> : diditei-4 katakamuka and alapadma outstretched <i>c</i> : front moṭita utplavana; diditei; muzhumaṇḍi to sama	
	tomtatakuntarita	takitatakಿತataka	————— Kartari utplavana (sides); diditei	
	Jamtaritakatōm kukuntari kitatōm	Takadimi-2; takadimitakadimi	Throw alternate legs forward from sama; kuttanam on kunčita	
	Tom ta tadimi takuntarita dingiṇatōm	Takita takita takadimi takita takita	<i>c,e,b</i> : karṭari utplavana (sides), motita utplavana (front); tei tei, diditei <i>a,b</i> : (2 nd tateitam 2 nd half) muzhumaṇḍi to garuda maṇḍala to bramari; teididitei	

XIV	Tāsām sankrīḍa mānānāmēṣavāditrāni hsvanaha	Takita takadimi	a: kunčita bhramari- self rotation e,b- utpluta (moṭita) bending torso d,c- teiyateihi; ēkapada bhramari with anga bhramari of torso

From the above description (table-1), an analysis of performance and presentation technique has been arrived at³. In set-I, five dancers make their entry from different wings: *a* & *b* from left front arch, *d* & *e* from before third right wing, *c* from before left third wing. It can be observed that their movements are not identical but there is similarity in the emphasis on the usage of torso- its gentle spin and sway both in bhramari and utplavana. These are similar to *mei* adavus that are done as preliminary adavus which prepare the body for the more strenuous korvais in items like jatīswaram or tillana. In this phrase too, the execution of these *mei* adavus which are gentle bhramaris and utplavanas help in three ways: being *mei* exercises that prepare the dancers for the successive korvai-s and tīrmanam-s, these adavus are executed in motion mainly to cover horizontal space- a significant aspect of group choreography on a proscenium. The lightness in placement of their feet and gentleness in the sway of the torso indicate a buoyant feel. Simultaneously, they evoke a sense of small swirls or ripples on the surface of the lake.

In contrast to the above, in set-II, the dancers break into a *usi* where they criss-cross the stage and form a trapezium (pattern-I). Momentum gathers from this stage on wherein subsequent movements with powerfully swift utplavana and *vēgini* bring *a* & *d* alternately intercrossing *c,e* and *b*.

³ The performance under analysis was viewed at the dance festivals at Kalakshetra auditorium, Chennai during the years 1997, 1998, 2001 & 2006

This opposite flow can be taken as a simple aesthetic pattern which provides a sense of heightened vitality. But, the rapidness of *a* and *d* and oppositional action seem to also suggest turbidity within the lake. Following this, simple kuṭhaṇa is used by *c,e* and *b* to go back with suggestive gestures of mridangam, tālam and veena. This clever usage of light feet movements in taḥimettu bring focus to their hastas which depict the musical instruments they carry. From their entry in set-I till the end of this set which ends in a simple teididitei, there is conspicuous usage of criss-cross rhythms initially paired between *ab*, *cd* and *e* and then between *ad* and *ceb*. This juxtaposes similarity and variation. The differences in action tend to get highlighted as there is a complementary but relative speed, changing body levels in action (*sama*, *aramaṇḍi*, *garuḍa stānaka*) and occasional oppositional and interlocking stream of movements. At the same time the kind of *adavus* executed blends in perfectly with the varying rhythms creating vibrancy.

Pattern-2 gives a lucid picture of the floor pattern of the five dancers where each one of them takes an individual parabolic path to move through a diagonal trapezium, which is a transitory position, to reach a pentagon formation. One thing that is visible throughout this scene is the fact that the trapezium, whether normal, inverted or diagonally placed, becomes a design motif from where different patterns begin, end or are transitory. This repetitive motif is significant in two ways: it acts as an intermediary position linking different dynamic patterns and their positioning gives ample scope for emphasis as a group and also as individual entities on proscenium.

A significant move which can be noticed in the set IV and set VI is the prominent usage of *utplavanas*, both *moṭita* and *kartari*, that create a sort of buoyant feel which seems like a virtual rush of ebb and flow. The formation of set VII, has *a* and *d* move alongside the upstage center when concurrently *c,b* and *e* move parallel but in opposite direction towards downstage right.

They draw apart, executing a fling of the right and then left leg with outstretched arms, an inclined body and a raised chin that maintains the line of the extended leg. This particular aḍavu exudes a majestic charm and flamboyant that is evidently felt from the beginning of the scene and which stays throughout. From here, *a and d* move diagonally together towards the downstage left in a rapid druta pace whereas *c, b and e* move parallel but backwards in a madhyama kāla čalana. Symmetry between uneven pairs is prominent here.

The set IX has an interesting mix of floor patterning as *a and d* run off stage through the front arch and *c, e and b* take centerstage. They play their instruments and dance to its tune. A typical triangular formation and an interchange of positions within this pattern using aerial kartari utplavana coupled with swift vėgini and a turn-around gives an ethereal touch of lightness that the heavenly apsaras bring to their dance. A stark contrast is the next pattern where linearity is highlighted with kuṭhana through tattimettu and ayata kuṭhana. Though the arm and feet movements are simple, they seem to distinctly convey an earthly heaviness, a contrast to the previous phrase. From showing the motions of the lake and the movements of the water nymphs, there is a sudden shift through which emphasises on the role of apsaras as the dancer with accompaniments where *c, b and e* become dancers and the remaining, the audience. Though limited to moving forward and backwards diagonally in taṭhimettu, the movement of *e* shows an effort by display, with a raised arm in prālamba hasta and left in ḍola flanked by *c* and *b* as her accompanists playing the mridangam and veena. This display of performance within a performance or dance within a dance shows the role of the dancer within a group in the already unfolding dance drama. This is a technique that Rukmini Devi uses to focus dancers in a group and to bring in group dances either in the form of tillana-s or daruvu-s or otherwise in to the narrative of a dance-drama. In set-X, bramari-s (ėkapada and kunćita) and diditei-s are majorly used to represent the changing pace, rise and fall of rhythm as well as to cover space and reach their positions. The dancers move with perfect poise along circular paths, as they progress smoothly and succinctly in a clockwise direction. The symmetry of synchronised fling and measured čalana brings in a feeling of purported ease and calmness. With a moṭita utplavana they scatter from the circle in different directions and get back to their initial trapezium formation.

Photo 1 (courtesy: Radhika Puthenedam)

For the next line in druta kala (set XII) the dancers who had dispersed come together to the centre again and position around *d* performs in moṭita mandala (photo-1). Interesting here are the levels between *d* in muzhumaṇḍi and *b, a, c* and *e* who are in sama levels. *b, a, c* and *e* stand with bhramara hasta arms outstretched and their glance- anuvritta drishti- follow the movement of their wrists-up and down. It produces the effect of water droplets falling on *d*. We may also presume that *d* is a water lily or lotus with other dancers surrounding it as bees or honey birds hovering around a full bloomed flower. They then again disperse to their positions with opening alapadma arms that suggest the profuseness of flowers around. Following this, all of them move to stage extremities with different torso moves in the same way that they made their entry- *a* doing a kunčita bhramari or self-rotation with bent knees, *e* and *b* an utpluta motita jump emphasising the torso bends towards sides, *d* and *c* doing ēkapada bhramari with a self-rotation along with anga brahmari of the torso. Dancers with different types of bhramaris move out as ripples ebbing into small waves that gently reach the shores of the lake.

Conclusion

Sabari Mōkṣam is frequent to many unworldly encounters. Magic realism is endowed with the grandeur of adbhuta in scenes that, wherewith, music emanates from the depths of a lake, encounter an enormous humongous beast of a bird in Jatāyu, an unwavering beseeching niṣācāri, the magical run of a golden deer, the awe of Ravana's court, kidnapping of Sita on the unearthly swift puṣpaka vimānam. *Sabari Mōkṣam* translates between the unearthly and the earthly as it also leads the audience towards reflecting upon the human poignancies like the

anger of Sita when she reprimands Lakshmana, pain of Lakshmana when he is unable to hear the doubting words of Sita, the sorrow of Rama on the loss of dear Sita or the anguish over friend Jatāyu's death.

The choreography of the sarōvara scene is such that it sets the pace for the rest of the drama. Rukmini Devi's usage of madhyama laya gati coupled with racy sprints of bhramaris, utplavanas and vēginis's along all possible directions across the stage appears to exert a dancer's compelling and competing urge to outlive the lifespan of an ebb nearing its end. The dancers rather disturb the unseen sage's penance through their dancing more than anything. The entire plot of *Sabari Mōkṣam* is racy and swift with many more characters making their appearances and dancing their parts. This way, the first scene with the description of *Panćapsara sarōvara* can be said to be offering a fantastic prologue to the unfolding drama. Fantastic, in their dance that entices every one by their sheer vibrancy, dynamism, brimming confidence and control over aspects of rhythm with a brilliant technical finesse.

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